

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTEGRATED RISK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF A BANKING GROUP

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Abstract

The article examines the conceptual foundations and structural elements of an integrated risk management system within a banking group. The purpose of the study is to systematize the key components, objectives, and governance principles of integrated risk management and to demonstrate its role in ensuring the financial stability and strategic sustainability of a banking group. The research is based on the analysis of theoretical approaches to risk management in financial institutions, international regulatory principles, and methodological frameworks applied in banking practice. The study uses methods of system analysis, comparative analysis, and structural modeling to identify the main elements and functional interrelations within the integrated risk management framework. The results of the study show that an effective integrated risk management system should operate simultaneously at the level of the entire banking group and at the level of its individual entities. The system integrates processes of risk identification, assessment, monitoring, reporting, and response, while also supporting risk-oriented decision-making and risk-adjusted performance evaluation. Special attention is paid to the role of corporate governance bodies, the definition of risk appetite, the development of a unified system of risk indicators, and the establishment of internal regulatory documentation and communication channels. The study concludes that the implementation of an integrated risk management system based on unified principles, methodologies, and information systems allows banking groups to maintain an optimal balance between profitability and risk exposure, improve the quality of managerial decision-making, and strengthen overall financial stability.

Keywords: integrated risk management, banking group, financial stability, risk appetite, corporate governance, risk monitoring.

The integrated risk management system of a financial group and/or a specific type of financial group and/or a banking subgroup (hereinafter referred to as the "Group") constitutes a set of interrelated components whose interaction enables the achievement of the Group's objectives and the fulfilment of its risk-management tasks. The components of a risk management system include the functions of the risk management system, the organization of that system, risk management processes, as well as the approaches, methodologies, tools, and information systems used within those processes (1).

The integrated risk management system operates at the level of the entire Group as a whole and at the level of its individual entities. The risk management system simultaneously functions at the level of the aggregate risk of the Group and its entities, as well as at the level of certain types of risk assumed by the Group and its entities. The approaches, methodologies and tools of the risk management system at the level of aggregate risk and certain types of risk should be presented in separate regulatory and methodological documents of the Group and its organizations, taking into account their technical complexity, diversity, and the need to regularly review them in the process of improving the risk management system.

The main objectives of the Group's integrated risk management system are to ensure the required level of financial stability of the Group and its entities, to ensure that the Group's risk profile corresponds to the strategic parameters of the Group's activities, and to develop and maintain a system of risk-response measures that is consistent with the profile and scope of the Group's operations.

Financial stability (2) is understood as the Group's ability to meet its obligations to third parties in full and in a timely manner; the adequacy of its equity capital to cover both expected and unexpected losses resulting from the realization of risks, with a probability that ensures the maintenance of solvency; the compliance of the Group's activities and those of its entities with the prudential standards and requirements of the national regulatory authorities of the countries in which they operate, including requirements related to capital adequacy of the Group and its entities; the presence of a balanced structure of assets and liabilities that ensures the necessary level of return on shareholders' equity.

As for the compliance of the Group's risk profile with the strategic parameters of the Group's activities, it is ensured through monitoring the actual values of risk indicators and taking appropriate response

measures when critical thresholds of risk indicators are reached.

A risk-response system (3, 4) is understood as a set of tools, the use of which makes it possible to influence the level of various types of risks. These tools should enable the reduction of the level of expected and/or unexpected losses associated with selected risks. The system of measures includes, in particular, hedging, diversification, insurance, limit-setting, and other tools. The system of risk response measures also includes a set of criteria that allow timely decision-making regarding the appropriateness of applying specific tools and determining which of them is most effective.

The key objectives of the integrated risk management system are (1):

- Defining risk appetite, which results in defining the Group's target level of financial stability and the aggregate level of risk that is acceptable to the Group in line with its strategy.
- Risk identification, i.e. the identification of risks that may affect the Group's current or planned operations.
- Risk assessment, that is, the qualitative or quantitative evaluation of expected and unexpected losses associated with each identified risk, the probability of incurring such losses, as well as the assessment of the aggregate level of risk assumed or planned to be assumed by the Group.
- Determining the amount of capital required to cover expected losses. This is an assessment of the amount of capital required by the Group to cover expected losses caused by the realization of the risks assumed by the Group (for the entire Group, for each entity within the Group, for each line of business).
- Determining the amount of capital required to cover unexpected losses. It is an assessment of the amount of capital required to cover unexpected losses caused by the realization of the risks assumed by the Group (for the entire Group, for each entity within the Group, for each line of business).
- Participation in risk-oriented decision-making. Supporting strategic and tactical decision-making processes by analyzing the impact of those decisions on the level of risk assumed by the Group, by informing the results of the analysis to those responsible for decision-making.
- Defining the target risk profile. Based on the Group's business strategy and plans, the Group's risk profile must be defined to ensure adherence to the established risk appetite.
- Establishment of a communication system. This includes the creation of communication channels that ensure the collection, processing and dissemination of risk-related information to all stakeholders. Maintaining a unified system of indicators for measuring risk levels; implementing and maintaining the information systems necessary for the operation of the communication channels.
- Creation of a permanent risk monitoring system. Development of a system of indicators that allows for constant monitoring of the current risk profile, in particular, allow assessment of the acceptability and justification of the level of each type of risk, as well as

monitor the compliance of the aggregate risk level with the established risk appetite.

- Risk reporting. This is the determination of actual values of risk indicators, the preparation of a report and its presentation to stakeholders, which makes it possible to assess the actual level of the Group's risk, the concentration of risks, the compliance of the types and levels of risks accepted with the target risk profile, as well as the compliance of the actual level of aggregate risk with the established risk appetite.

- Identifying accessible methods for managing risk and evaluating their effectiveness. This is the formation of a set of tools that can be used to influence the level of various types of risks accepted, as well as assessing the effectiveness of their use, taking into account the cost of application and/or the foregone profit associated with refusing to accept the risk.

- Timely response to risk, which involves identifying situations that require taking measures to influence the level of risk and to select the most effective tools for this.

- Risk-adjusted performance evaluation. Assessment of the effectiveness of activities, taking into account risk. The assessment of the various entities of the Group and their individual areas of activity, taking into account both the financial results obtained and the level of risk they accept in order to make a profit, as well as the volume of economic capital allocated to these entities and aimed at covering unforeseen losses due to the impact of risks. The assessment of strategic initiatives and new projects, taking into account their impact on the level of risk to which the Group is exposed.

- Creation of an internal regulatory documentation system for risk management. The creation of effective risk management processes and procedures that ensure an integrated approach to managing all risks of the Group, as well as the documentation of these processes and procedures through an internal regulatory documentation system.

- Monitoring compliance with the requirements for internal risk management regulatory documentation. It involves overseeing the implementation of the risk management processes and procedures set forth in the internal documentation.

- Improvement of risk management processes. This is the assessment of the effectiveness of risk management processes, including verifying the implementation of all assumptions underlying the risk assessment methodologies, implementing measures to improve the quality of risk management based on the results of the assessment of the effectiveness of risk management processes.

The Integrated risk management system combines both the Group's risk identification and actual risk assessment functions, as well as preventive risk management functions. Accordingly, governing bodies and departments ensuring the operation of the risk management system exercise control over the compliance of the risk level with the established restrictions, as well as participate in the adoption of management decisions at various levels that affect changes in the risk level in the future.

The participation of the bank's Board of Directors, its Management Board, and the bank's specialized committees in the risk management system must be implemented through the following principles (1, 5):

- Management decisions must be made with due consideration of their impact on the level of risk affecting the Group and its entities.
- The Board of Directors is responsible for the overall risk management performance of the Group. The Board regularly monitors the risk level, which the Group adopts based on both aggregate risk indicators and reports that include qualitative and quantitative indicators of different types of risks.

The Bank's Board of Directors, the bank's management, and the bank's specialized committees: as bodies authorized to exercise oversight within the Group, have the ability through corporate governance procedures to exercise oversight over the activities of subsidiaries, the state of the risk management system and its effectiveness, based on reports on the level of risks taken by the Group and on breaches of the limits set by the risk appetite. Risk management processes are integrated into strategic planning and management processes. In particular, the development of the strategy and the definition of priority development directions and strategic objectives are carried out taking into account the balance between the desired profitability and the magnitude of the risks taken by the Group. The impact of the strategic decisions taken on the risk profile of the Group, individual entities of the Group, as well as other indicators of the Group's risk level is subject to discussion.

Risk management is a continuous process that must be integrated into the processes carried out by the organizations and units within the Group, including:

- Integration should be implemented through strict documentation of processes and operations and the inclusion of control procedures in them, which make it possible to prevent violations of the restrictions set on the risk level, as well as to monitor the actual level of risk. Specifically, a system of risk indicators is implemented, and permissible values that these indicators can assume are being proposed.
- The authority to accept each type of risk should be assigned to the management bodies, managers and employees of all levels of each organization of the Group. The distribution of authority and responsibility for accepting risks between collegial bodies, as well as managers and employees of different levels of management, should be carried out in accordance with the Group's strategy and the corporate governance principles adopted in the Group.
- The effectiveness of risk management at the level of business processes must also be ensured by all employees taking into account the risks associated with their decisions or actions, as well as by defining their responsibility for complying with risk management standards and procedures.

The Group must have a unified integrated risk management system, through which risks that could affect the operation of any of the organizations within the Group are managed.

Risk management processes based on unified risk management principles should be implemented in all organizations within the Group and unified risk assessment methodologies should be used, taking into account their affiliation with the type of organization. Moreover, each organization's risk management processes must be sufficiently adapted to the specifics of its business and take into account the specifics of the risks to which it is exposed.

The Group must implement a risk management system that can have a significant impact on the activities of its constituent organizations. The management of risks inherent to financial organizations is of primary importance: credit risk (including country risk), market risk (including price, currency and interest rate risks, as well as market liquidity risk), liquidity risk, operational risk, legal risk, reputational risk, compliance risk and strategic risk. The principles, approaches, methodologies and tools for influencing the level of risks listed above should be developed for the entire Group and adapted for each of the Group's financial institutions, thereby achieving uniformity of technical means and methodological approaches to risk management in the Group.

The independence of the risk management department can be ensured by implementing the following principles (1, 6):

- The Group must have a department that coordinates the risk management of the Group's entities. This department is independent of the departments carrying out operational activities, which is ensured by its inclusion in the risk management unit, which is directly subordinate to the sole executive body of the Group's parent organization (the chairman of the bank's board).
- Risk management departments within the Group's organizations must be independent of other departments within those organizations and must conduct their activities in accordance with the Group's risk management standards, as well as report information about the results of their activities to the department coordinating the Group's risk management.
- Within the Group, responsibility for coordinating the management of legal risk, business reputation risk, and compliance risk should be placed on the bank's relevant departments, which carry out the methodological coordination of the Group's risk management activities. These departments should be responsible for the development and implementation of legal risk, reputational risk management policies and compliance risk policies, as well as for the implementation of these risk management processes at the Group and its individual entity levels. The responsibility for coordinating strategic risk management should be placed on the bank's division that performs this function both at the bank level and at the level of its subsidiaries and affiliates.

Independent oversight of the risk management system to assess its effectiveness and verify compliance with and full implementation of risk management procedures should be carried out periodically by the internal control/audit departments of the Group and its constituent entities. The oversight is carried out both at the Group level and at the level of each constituent entity.

The objects of control are both risk management processes and those elements of risk management that are integrated into strategic management and other operational processes.

The overall effectiveness of the risk management system is overseen by the Bank's Board of Directors and the Management Board based on regular reports that must be provided by the Group's risk management coordination unit, as well as the Group's internal control/audit unit, based on the results of inspection activities.

Findings. The study demonstrates that an effective integrated risk management system should function simultaneously at the level of the banking group as a whole and at the level of its individual entities. Such a system integrates risk identification, assessment, monitoring, reporting, and response processes into strategic planning and operational management. Particular attention is paid to the definition of risk appetite, the development of a unified system of risk indicators, risk-adjusted performance evaluation, and the role of corporate governance bodies in overseeing risk exposure. The integration of these elements ensures consistency between the group's risk profile and its strategic objectives.

Originality/value. The paper proposes a structured approach to organizing integrated risk management in banking groups, emphasizing the coordination of risk management processes, unified methodologies,

and corporate governance mechanisms. The proposed framework contributes to improving managerial decision-making and strengthening the financial stability of banking groups.

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